

SECTION OF BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES

MANUFACTURING OF REMOVABLE LAMELLAR DENTURES FOR ELDERLY AND SENILE PATIENTS

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Abstract

Orthopedic treatment of complete tooth loss in elderly and senile patients is associated with certain difficulties, taking into account the mental and somatic status of the patient. Functional and physiological changes inevitably occur in the organs and tissues of the maxillofacial area and the whole body: hormonal, muscular, digestive, etc. With age, the epithelial layer of the oral mucosa undergoes atrophy, elastic fibers disappear in the submucosal layer, and the vascularization of soft tissues worsens. The mucous membrane becomes sensitive and easily vulnerable.

Keywords: complex of treatment methods, plate prostheses, terms of use of prostheses.

Despite this, gerontostomatology remains one of the most relevant areas in dentistry today. WHO has set a goal to reduce the number of elderly and senile patients with unbalanced occlusion (with missing teeth and/or dentures requiring replacement) to 10% of the total number of people in this age group.

Psychologists say that an elderly person who exists harmoniously in society and feels like a full-fledged member of society ages more slowly, unlike their peers who do not maintain social connections, live in isolation and therefore do not have the desire to maintain themselves in proper physical and aesthetic shape. Thus, we understand that a fully functioning dentofacial system is a factor that slows down premature aging, providing an elderly person with certain social and psychological benefits - an aesthetic appearance, a feeling of mental comfort, the ability to chew food normally, fully perceive its taste, and not experience difficulties in communication.

With age, and especially with the loss of teeth, the maxillofacial area undergoes serious changes in the external structure and internal structure of the entire dental system. The higher the age and the more time has passed since the loss of teeth, the more significant the changes.

The purpose of the study - is to determine the optimal set of methods for dental treatment of patients in older age groups with removable plate dentures.

Materials and methods. 110 elderly patients, Methodology for manufacturing a soft lining of a removable denture, made by a laboratory method. The Microclean device is a device for carrying out the method of mechanical cleaning of dentures. The use of a complex of artificial saliva xerostom at the rehabilitation and preventive stage of prosthetics. Along with

age-related changes in the maxillofacial area, exceeding the period of use of existing removable dentures significantly complicates prosthetics for patients in older age groups. A survey of 125 elderly patients, residents of Moscow, who use removable dentures, showed that only 19% of those surveyed had removable dentures manufactured less than 5 years ago (with recommended terms of use); in 71% of patients, the terms of use were significantly exceeded.

Results. Duration of use of removable dentures: less than 5 years - 19%; more than 5 years - 35%; more than 10 years - 33%; more than 20 years - 13%. Many authors note a significant decrease in the adaptive capabilities of gerontodental patients. Due to the uncontrolled use of removable dentures, patients experienced unsatisfactory fixation, inconsistency (reduction) of the boundaries of the dentures with the prosthetic bed, significant abrasion of artificial teeth, up to complete abrasion of anatomical structures. Among patients using dentures for more than 5 years or more, 80% had new dentures made, sometimes several, which they could not use and continued to use the "old" familiar dentures. Conducted stereognastic testing ("Stereognosis", Landt H., 1979) to assess adaptive capabilities showed that gerontodental patients identify test objects 2.5 times slower compared to patients of middle age groups and make 3 times more errors. Taking into account the progressive age-related changes in the maxillofacial area and the significant decrease in the adaptive capabilities of patients in older age groups, the nature of the use of prostheses also has its own characteristics. Among 125 examined elderly patients, residents of Moscow, 41% have prostheses, but do not use them; 34% use prosthetics constantly; 13% use dentures only when eating, 12% use dentures during communication

(conversation). Gerontology distinguishes the biological and calendar age of elderly patients; of course, each patient of this age group has his own individual characteristics of the severity of age-related physiological or pathological changes, as well as the possibility of a difference or coincidence of the calendar and biological age, however, it is also indisputable that a large number of gerontological patients have the presence of concomitant diseases (the most common diseases), such as cardiovascular diseases; diseases of the gastrointestinal tract; malignant neoplasms; diabetes Long-term use of drugs used for these pathologies causes dry mouth. Taking into account degenerative changes in the salivary glands, along with taking medications, elderly and senile patients experience xerostomia, which in turn negatively affects the fixation of removable laminar dentures and their hygienic condition.

Conclusions. In the presence of pronounced changes in the alveolar parts of the jaws (especially the lower jaw), low pliability of the mucous membrane, and in the presence of severe pain, the manufacture of removable dentures with a soft lining is recommended. As part of dispensary observation, it is necessary to carry out mechanical cleaning of removable dentures using the Microclean apparatus. If you have dentures (without exceeding the recommended period of use), it is necessary to correct them: restoring the height of the lower part of the face, replacing artificial teeth (in case of abrasion, breakage) or installing artificial teeth to replace lost teeth. If it is impossible to use previous dentures (poor hygienic condition of the dentures, numerous breakdowns and repairs, significant abrasion of more than 30% of all artificial teeth), production of new removable dentures, “copying” the shape of the teeth and dental arches of the old “habitual” dentures. Taking into account age-related changes (degenerative changes in the salivary glands), long-term use of pharmacological drugs is possible – as a result, a decrease in the total amount of mixed saliva; after prosthetics for elderly patients, recommendations for the use of a gel – a saliva substitute are required to reduce the time of adaptation

to prostheses, ensuring a higher hygienic state of the prostheses, creating a high degree of fixation of removable dentures. Dispensary observation of elderly patients is mandatory, once every 6 months. In orthopedic treatment of this special category of patients, it is important to be patient and conduct explanatory conversations at each clinical stage. It is necessary to take into account individual age-related changes in the maxillo-facial area, especially psycho-emotional status.

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